

Principles of Reactive Interfacial Chemical Cleaning

by

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Abstract

This paper introduces the principles of 'Reactive Interfacial Chemical Cleaning', a technique that is widely used in many high-tech industries to clean contaminated parts. The two key steps in this process, mass transport and reaction kinetics, are described briefly. One dimensional cleaning models are developed for both steady state and unsteady state situations, and contaminant etch rates are predicted. Special attention is given to physical descriptions during model formulation rather than detailed mathematics. Cleaning analysis is extended to multidimensional problems with the aid of a two dimensional example. The finite element method is used as the computational technique to simulate this model problem. The role of dimensionless groups such as the Reynolds number, bulk Peclet number, Damkohler number, Schmidt number and Sherwood number is emphasized through out this study. It is shown that an increase in the values of any of these dimensionless groups leads to an increase in contaminant removal rates and hence the cleaning process.

1.0 Introduction

Cleaning of materials and equipment is an integral part of many high tech operations such as those in the semiconductor, disk drive, aircraft and medical industries. The aim of any cleaning process is to remove one or more specified materials, called contaminants, from a parent material that needs to be rendered clean. Contaminants can be removed either by physical or chemical means, or a combination of both.

A physical mechanism for contaminant removal can be defined as one which involves detachment of the contaminant from the parent material by not changing its chemical composition. For example, a thin film of oil can be removed from a metal by bringing it in contact with a surfactant solution, usually with some form of agitation. In a very simplified view the oil detaches from the metal due to decreased adhesion, brought about by the surface active properties of the surfactant. The detached oil is encapsulated in a sheath of surfactant molecules forming a stable oil in water emulsion, and preventing its re-deposition onto the metal surface. At the end of this process oil continues to exist as oil, and its chemical composition remains unchanged. Another example is that of the removal of a thin film of water from a metal surface. A water film is considered to be a contaminant in most semiconductor processes. Removal of water by evaporating the water is a physical process, since the chemical composition of liquid water and its vapor are the same.

The second category of contaminant removal, through chemical means, involves a chemical reaction that modifies the chemical composition of the contaminant. For example, during the manufacture of semiconductor IC's, aluminum metal is deposited to form metallic contacts in a process called metallization [1]. Besides deposition on the IC, the aluminum is also deposited on the walls and body of the processing equipment, contaminating it. Such contamination is detrimental to further processing, especially if the same equipment is used to deposit a variety of thin films. In fact, a few atoms of aluminum wrongly transferred onto the IC, in an intermediate doping process step, will destroy the performance of the final product. Therefore, it becomes imperative to remove the accumulated metal from the process equipment at regular intervals. Now, the question is how to remove the aluminum metal from the process equipment. One method of successfully removing it is to bring the equipment in contact with a chemical solution that reacts readily with the aluminum, but not with the parent equipment material. If the equipment were made of stainless steel, any alkali such as sodium hydroxide would do the job. The aluminum would selectively react with the alkali, forming new compounds, such as aluminates. The end result is a conversion of the aluminum metal to a new material, an aluminate, which consists of aluminum, oxygen and an alkali metal such as sodium, if sodium hydroxide was used. This technique of cleaning is commonly referred to as chemical cleaning or etching in the industry. It may be noted that this process is usually irreversible, and that there is no easy way to re-generate the contaminant back to its original chemical form.

Cleaning using chemical reactions is not always as trivial as depicted in the above example. In many real situations in industry a wide variety of metals and chemicals are used during processing, which contaminate process equipment with a combination of materials. Further, the contaminant deposition could be in multi-layers, with a variation in the deposition thickness and distribution on the surface. In such practical situations it may be impossible to obtain a chemical solution that has complete selectivity to the contaminant. One often poses the question whether it is possible to clean without destroying the part, and whether it is possible to prolong its cycle life. In view of the high dollar value of the equipment this issue becomes increasingly important. Therefore, the big question, in the absence of other alternate cleaning methods, is how to make the best use of chemical cleaning to effectively and successfully remove contaminants.

Traditionally, cleaning professionals have approached this problem by focusing heavily on the formulation of chemical recipes and its straight forward use, which consists of part immersion in these chemical concoctions for a certain duration of time. There has been little or no direct effort in elucidating the etching mechanisms for different systems, gathering systematic scientific data on etch rates under different conditions, and understanding the dynamics and factors that influence chemical cleaning. A strong scientific base has been the corner stone of all high tech industries that use clean process parts and which require cleaning as a necessary process step. Therefore, it is highly desirable for the cleaning industry to also stand on an equivalent scientific platform. With this in perspective and also noting that an effective and successful use of chemical cleaning is required, it becomes very critical for the cleaning professional to have access to all relevant scientific information. It is only through this knowledge base that intelligent decisions on the etch time and etch chemistry can be made.

The theme of this paper is to describe this knowledge base and introduce the principles that govern reactive chemical etching at solid/fluid interfaces. The acronym RICC will be used in place of the phrase 'Reactive Interfacial Chemical Cleaning' for brevity.

The contents in this paper will also be useful to cleaning professionals who use physical methods for cleaning, since detachment of contaminants can be modeled as physical reactions. Further, the insights developed in the dynamic situation, such as cleaning in the presence of fluid flow, is applicable to both classifications. In the present decade, in addition to the gross contaminant removal, there is a heavy emphasis on the cosmetic appearance of the part after cleaning. This issue is of great importance to original equipment manufacturers, who often require chemical etching to remove weld scale contaminants and/or etch a very thin layer of the surface to remove embedded contaminants during machining. A large majority resort to this step to improve the cosmetic appearance, since a cosmetically acceptable part can enhance the value of the product, in some cases leading to its acceptance or rejection. The contents in this paper will reflect on this issue and add some insights. Finally, professionals in the wet chemical etching field, used for pattern generation in the semiconductor industry, will find the information here of some use too. This is because the scientific fundamentals of chemical cleaning and wet etching processes are the same.

2.0 The real cleaning process

Schematics of what happens in the real cleaning process is shown in Figure 1. At the core of this problem is a parent material (P) contaminated with a material (B), immersed in an etchant material (A). The word ‘material’ is used here to reflect that it could be organic or inorganic in composition, and also that it could contain more than one chemical species. The etchant is transported first from the bulk to the solid/fluid interface. At this interface a chemical reaction takes place, which could be irreversible or reversible, and can be symbolically written as follows.

Here, the small letters refer to the molar stoichiometric coefficients that take part in the reaction. Note that in general a host of products could form such as R and S. Also, in the reaction shown, allowance is provided for the parent material to react. If the product moles p’ is the same as reactant moles p, then the parent material is not consumed and the two are identically equal to zero. After the products are formed, which might be a solid and/or a gas, they could remain attached to the interface and/or be transported to other regions in the domain. The domain typically consists of the entire system in which the cleaning takes place, which could be a simple tank or a special reactor.

To understand, describe and predict the cleaning that takes place in the real process described above, it is necessary to have a thorough grasp of what is happening during two key steps. The first is to do with the ‘transport’ of chemical species to and away from the interface, and the second is to do with the reaction that is occurring at the interface. These topics will be discussed in detail in the sections to follow. The real cleaning problem in the true sense is three dimensional in nature and is extremely complex to tackle in its entirety. However, as with the analysis of most scientific problems, the real problem is modeled as a simpler set of problems. Many a time the simplified problem can mimic the true situation, as will become evident in the sections to follow. Further, the insights obtained in tackling the simplified set of problems enables us to make intelligent predictions in the more complex situation.

3.0 Transport theory - basics

Transport of chemical species in a fluid (liquid or gas) takes place by some very well known mechanisms, and have been researched extensively. The general transport theory is quite mathematical and complex in nature and the interested reader is referred to *Bird et al.* for details [2]. However, from the perspective of this paper, it is sufficient to recognize that matter can be transported by two principal mechanisms, *diffusion* and *convection*.

Diffusion is basically the movement of a chemical species due to a concentration difference, more precisely a chemical potential difference. For example, if a drop of blue ink is gently added to a glass of stagnant water, the ink begins to diffuse throughout until the color becomes uniform every where. The uniform color implies that the ink concentration is

constant in the entire domain. At this stage the rates of ink movement in the bulk by diffusion reduces to practically zero, since there is no concentration difference driving force. Diffusion rates are predicted by the well known Fick's law, shown below.

$$\mathbf{J}_i = -D_i \nabla c_i \quad (2)$$

Here, J_i is the *molar flux* of species i with respect to the molar average velocity, ∇c_i is *concentration gradient* (the symbol ∇ is a compact mathematical way of describing spatial variation) of species i , and D_i is the *diffusion coefficient* of species i in a mixture. Therefore, in order to predict diffusive fluxes one has to have a knowledge of diffusion coefficients, which is obtained usually from actual experiments. These have been tabulated for many known systems and further information can be obtained from *Bird et al. [2]*.

Mass transport by convection, on the other hand, is movement of a species due to bulk motion of the fluid itself. That is, a species i is carried from one location to another literally by the fluid motion. In the example for diffusion above, if the liquid in the glass was stirred, then the blue ink would be transported by convection due to fluid motion, in addition to diffusion. Prediction of mass transfer rates by convection has also been researched extensively, and it is common to express it as follows:

$$N_{i,y} = k_m \Delta c_i \quad (3)$$

Here, $N_{i,y}$ is the molar/mass flux in the y -direction, relative to a stationary coordinate system, and k_m is the convective *mass transfer coefficient* based on the concentration driving force, Δc_i . This driving force is simply the algebraic difference in concentration between two locations, where the values can be determined quite conveniently. The mass transfer coefficient is highly dependent on the dynamics of fluid flow, thermal conditions, and on the geometry of the system. Prediction of this coefficient is possible through several correlations developed over the years and a good introduction is available in the text by *Treybal[3]*. Note that the inverse of k_m is the resistance to this rate process. In the field of transport phenomena it is common to reduce the complex rate processes to forms where the flux is expressed as a driving force divided by a resistance. Besides providing useful physical insights into the actual process, it also simplifies secondary analysis.

The etch rates in RICC would vary depending on the relative importance of the two transport mechanisms, diffusion and convection. In many practical situations a combination of both mechanisms may be needed to account for the etchant transport. In such situations an increasingly popular approach is to simulate the full blown transport problem computationally, and the versatility of this approach will be demonstrated later in this paper.

4.0 Reaction kinetics - basics

Describing a reaction involves specifying the reaction mechanism and the rate at which it is taking place. The subject of reaction kinetics and reactor theory has traditionally enjoyed an important role in chemical engineering, and there is a large mass of literature available in this area. The fundamentals can be found in many published texts, such as that by *Levenspiel*[4]. From a cleaning view point it is necessary to recognize that the reactions are *heterogeneous*, since two different phases, solid and fluid, are present at the reaction interface. Prediction of reaction rates for heterogeneous systems is not an easy task, since the rate expressions are quite complex as shown in equation (4).

$$r_i = \text{Function of (system pressure, temperature, concentration distribution of reactants, mass transport conditions, solid surface properties and composition, wetting behavior, fluid flow, system geometry, crystal structure,)} \quad (4)$$

The reaction rate, r_i is expressed in units of moles or mass of species i reacting per unit surface area of the solid, per unit time. The specific functional form of equation (4) is established through experiments. On a related topic, it is interesting to note that the complex functional form of the reaction rate can give reasonable explanations on the occurrence of cosmetic artifacts. Local variations in the factors shown in the functional form, lead to varying degrees of local reaction rates, and hence can result in surface appearance differences.

In RICC one is interested in actually predicting the etch rates of contaminants, so it is necessary to establish a tangible functional form for the reaction rate. To simplify the analysis a popular approach has been to assume that the reaction rate is a strong function of temperature and reactant concentration, so that equation (4) can be rewritten as:

$$r_i = k_r (\text{Function of concentration}) \quad (5)$$

k_r is called the *reaction rate constant* and is a strong function of temperature [3]. In many practical situations the functional form reduces to a linear, quadratic or a power dependency of the concentration of the reacting species. For example, the reaction rate of contaminant B in terms of the etchant A, as shown in equation (1), can be cast in the following linear form.

$$r_B = k_r \cdot b \cdot c_A \quad (6)$$

Such a model assumption is of practical use only when it can predict real conditions. Once a model for the reaction rate is justified, the parameters required such as k_r are obtained from actual experiments.

To predict the change in contamination thickness with time, the importance of mass transport and reaction kinetics has to be weighed against each other. One often speaks as to

which of the two is limiting the rate of contaminant removal. For example, if the rate of reaction is very fast at the interface, then the rate at which new etchant arrives limits how fast the contaminant can be removed. In this situation the RICC process is said to be *mass transport limited*. On the other hand, if the rate of reaction is very slow compared to the arrival of etchant at the interface, the process is termed *reaction rate limited*. Sometimes, both mass transport and reaction kinetics are important, and have to be taken into account for a realistic prediction.

5.0 1-D cleaning models

Transport of etchant species to the interface can occur in one, two or three dimensions. In the case of one dimensional transport, especially in the direction of desired etching, analytical expressions can be derived to predict the etch rates. This process involves predicting the location of the interface as a function of time. Therefore, this class of problems fall into the category of moving boundary problems. An example of a 1-D model is that of a contaminant whose linear surface dimension is much large compared to its thickness, immersed in an etchant that is stationary or in unidirectional motion parallel to the surface. One dimensional models are useful in practice and serve as a starting point in describing RICC.

It is important to note that there is no single universal one dimensional etching model. Any model that is established is done so within a set of constraints and assumptions. There is no problem with making initial assumptions, provided the resulting predictive equations describe the real phenomena. Some important models and their limitations are discussed below.

5.1 Steady state solutions

To begin with it will be assumed that a single component in the contaminant, and a single component in the etchant are the active reactive species. A steady state solution exists if the value of the etchant concentration at any point in the domain does not change with time. This is possible if the quantity of etchant is large enough so that dissolution of contaminant does not appreciably change its bulk concentration. Note that the concentration of the etchant is not necessarily the same everywhere and that it varies spatially, decreasing as one approaches the interface. Further, it will be assumed that the concentration of etchant at the interface is negligible compared to that in the bulk, due to a reaction here, and will be considered equal to zero. The contaminant will be considered to be in the form of a thin sheet, with its surface dimensions being large compared to its thickness.

The three models to be discussed will all be based on the *unreacted core model*. This model suggests that the reaction interface moves into the original contaminant solid as time progresses, leaving behind a product layer such as R and S in equation (1), typically called

smut. In what follows, details of associated mathematics will be avoided for reasons of simplicity and brevity. Interested readers can refer to [4] for mathematical details, where expressions have been derived for an analogous situation.

5.1.1 Reaction kinetics limited model

Figure 2 (a) : Contaminant geometry as cleaning progresses.

Figure 2 (b) : Concentration profile of etchant solution (A) for the reaction kinetics limited model.

In this model the rate at which the etchant arrives at the interface is much greater than the rate at which reaction takes place. The reaction is the same as that in equation 1, except that the parent materials are inert. Figure 2 (a) shows the geometry of the contaminant, with the etching direction taken to be along the vertical y -axis. The location of the interface at any time, t , is given by $y(t)$ and will be identified as y_i . The initial contaminant thickness is H . Figure 2 (b) shows the concentration distribution corresponding to figure 2 (a). The concentration is uniform everywhere and equal to the bulk etchant concentration, c_{Ai} , except at the interface where it is zero. The form of the reaction rate will be chosen to be linear, as

shown in equation (6), with c_A being set to c_{A1} . The required etch rate equation is obtained by balancing the change in the mass of contaminant to the rate of reaction, and is shown below.

$$\text{Thickness etched} = (H - y_i) = \alpha_1 t \quad (7)$$

$$\text{and, } \alpha_1 = \text{constant for a given system} = (M_B b k_r c_{A1} / \rho_B) \quad (8)$$

The meaning of the symbols shown here, or elsewhere, can be found in the nomenclature at the end of this paper. The important thing to note is that the constant can be evaluated from data available in standard tables.

This simple model predicts a linear relationship between the thickness etched and time elapsed. To test whether a real RICC process can be predicted by this model, one can carry out simple measurements of thickness etched versus time. If the data falls on a straight line and has a slope equal to that predicted by equation (8), then the model is valid in this case. Sometimes in situations where k_r is not readily available, this method of testing for the applicability of the model may not be possible. An alternate testing procedure would be to conduct a set of similar experiments, but with c_{A1} maintained at different values for each test. If the new slopes are still linear, but with different magnitudes, the model would be valid provided the ratio of slopes is equal to the ratio of concentrations used in the test. This is because k_r is a strong function of temperature, but not concentration. Note that once the model validity is established, k_r can literally be back calculated from the experimental slopes.

The simple model also gives additional insights. For example, one may be interested in etching the contaminant faster, since turnaround time in cleaning is of great importance to end users. Faster etching is possible if the temperature is increased, since k_r would increase, and/or if the bulk etchant concentration, c_{A1} , is increased. These increases show up as an increase in α_1 which predicts a greater etch rate through equation (7). Also, note that the etch rate for a given system is a constant and equal to α_1 , under the constraints of this model.

5.1.2 Mass transport limited model

This situation is the other extreme of the previous case. In this model the rate of reaction is much greater compared to the rate at which mass arrives at the interface. Figures 3 (a) and (b) show the schematics of this model. The entire resistance to mass transport is limited to a diffusion region of thickness, δ , where the concentration changes from C_{A1} to zero. The smut is assumed to offer no resistance to mass transport. Therefore, the required etching equation is obtained by equating the rate of mass transfer to the change in mass of the contaminant, and is given below.

$$\text{Thickness etched} = (H - y_i) = \alpha_2 t \quad (9)$$

$$\text{and, } \alpha_2 = \text{constant for a given system} = (M_B b k_{meq} c_{A1} / \rho_B) \quad (10)$$

The variable k_{meq} is equal to D_A/δ if molecular diffusion dominates the mass transport, and is equal to k_m if convective transport dominates. Though k_{meq} can be evaluated from theory, a better approach is to evaluate α_2 directly from experiments. One could conduct experiments and plot thickness etched versus time. If the slope is linear, then equation (9) could be applicable. But, in view of the model in section 4.1.1.) the mass transfer limitation should be verified. This can be done by increasing the fluid velocity parallel to the interface and verifying whether the etching is linear with time.

Figure 3 (a) : Contaminant geometry as cleaning progresses.

Figure 3 (b) : Concentration profile of etchant solution (A) for the mass transport limited model.

If it is known *a priori* that the etching is mass transfer limited, the theoretical determination of α_2 must be done with care. If diffusion is dominating the distance δ must reflect the actual diffusion path. If convection is dominating then k_m must be evaluated from a correlation that is appropriate for the given situation. For example, for the flow past a flat plate the correlation below can be used [3].

$$Sh = 0.664 Re_x^{0.5} Sc^{0.333} \quad (11)$$

This equation contains three important dimensionless groups. Their significance and definitions are described below. More will be said about dimensionless groups in section 6.0.

$$\text{Re}_x = \text{Reynolds number} = \frac{\text{Inertial forces}}{\text{Viscous forces}} = \frac{L_x U \rho}{\mu} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{Sh} = \text{Sherwood number} = \frac{\text{Diffusional resistance to mass transfer}}{\text{Convective resistance to mass transfer}} = \frac{k_m L}{D_A} \quad (13)$$

$$\text{Sc} = \text{Schmidt number} = \frac{\text{Molecular diffusivity of momentum}}{\text{Molecular diffusivity of mass}} = \frac{\mu}{\rho D_A} \quad (14)$$

Here, L_x is the linear dimension along the contaminant surface, measured from the leading edge, which is the location where the flow first enters the vicinity of the surface. On the other hand, L , is a characteristic length scale of the system. For a flat contaminant surface, this could be the square root of the surface area or the length of one side of the surface. Note that equation (11) is valid only for values of Re_x less than 50,000.

5.1.3 Diffusion in smut layer limited model

Reaction products are an inevitable part of any etching process. These products could be solids and/or gases. For example, when metals react with an acid, the by-products formed are hydrogen gas and a solid metal salt (smut). The solids formed may dissolve in the bulk etchant as ions, or may simply form a layer of product deposits. In the latter situation, etching rates can dramatically reduce if the smut layer offers resistance to etchant transport. This situation is tackled in the present model.

Figures 4 (a) and (b) show the schematics of the smut layer controlled model. In this model, the entire resistance to mass transfer and the change in concentration gradient occurs in the smut layer. During etching, under these conditions, the surrounding concentration profile changes with time and the process is really unsteady. However, the rate at which the contaminant decreases in thickness is far less than the rate of etchant diffusion. In such cases the concentration field can be considered to be invariant within a specified time interval, and a pseudo steady state analysis can be carried out. Such an analysis, after taking into account a balance between the change in contaminant mass and the diffusive flux of the etchant in the smut layer, yields the following etching expression [4].

$$\text{Thickness etched} = (H - y_i) = \alpha_3 (t)^{0.5} \quad (15)$$

$$\alpha_3 = \text{constant for a given system} = (2 M_B b D_{A,\text{eff}} c_{A1} / \rho_B)^{0.5} \quad (16)$$

This mechanism of etching can be easily recognized by its square root of time dependency. Note that $D_{A,\text{eff}}$ in equation (16) is an effective diffusion coefficient for the diffusion of the etchant through the smut layer. The constant α_3 can be best evaluated by taking the slope of an experimental plot of the thickness etched versus the square root of time.

Figure 4 (a) : Contaminant geometry as cleaning progresses. The smut layer can be removed by mechanical scrubbing.

Figure 4 (b) : Concentration profile of etchant solution (A) for the diffusion in smut layer limited model.

5.2 Unsteady state solutions

Unsteady state etching processes are those in which the etchant concentration changes with time spatially. This would typically occur when small amounts of etchant loss, due to reaction with the contaminant, changes the etchant concentration appreciably. Analysis of unsteady state problems are more complex than steady state problems. This is because at any instant of time both the concentration field and the location of the contaminant interface are an unknown. Derivation of exact analytical expressions for unsteady state etching is not possible, except for the situation of one dimensional etching. This case is considered here.

The problem configuration is shown in figures 5 (a) and 5 (b). The initial condition for this problem is that the concentration is uniform everywhere and equal to c_{A1} . This condition is valid at all times prior to the start of etching ($t < 0$). After etching starts ($t \geq 0$) the concentration field is non-uniform and is bounded by two boundary conditions. The first one states that the concentration of etchant at distances far away from the contaminant is equal to c_{A1} . The second one states that at the interface the loss of contaminant mass is equal to the

flux of etchant by diffusion. These initial conditions and boundary conditions are applied as constraints to the general equation for the conservation of etchant species. This involves solving a partial differential equation and the relevant mathematics can be found in the paper by *Kuiken et al.* [5]. The resulting etching expression is shown below.

$$\text{Thickness etched} = (H - y_i) = 2 \gamma (D_A t)^{0.5}$$

The factor γ in this equation is a result of the complicated math associated with the solution to this problem. For a given system it can be directly read off from the graph in figure 6. To do this the system dependent variable, β , needs to be evaluated first using the expression shown below.

$$\beta = \rho_B / (M_B b c_{A1}) \quad (18)$$

Equation (17) implies that unsteady state etching shows a square root dependency with time. Testing whether this model is applicable is straight forward. This can be done by plotting experimental values of thickness etched versus the square root of time, and verifying whether the measured slope is constant and equal to $2 \gamma (D_A)^{0.5}$.

Figure 5 (a) : Contaminant geometry with progression of etching.

Figure 5 (b) : Concentration profiles of etchant solution (A) at different instances of time.

Figure 6 : Graphical plot to estimate the factor γ for specified β values [1, 5].

6.0 2-D cleaning models

In earlier sections it was emphasized that mass transport and reactions kinetics form the basis for describing RICC. In this regard 1-D models were discussed. Problems can be tackled as one dimensional when the etchant concentration is a function of only one spatial dimension, such as the y-direction in the models previously discussed, and if the reaction kinetics are isotropic along the surface. If this is not the case then the problem is multi-dimensional (2D or 3D). Multi-dimensional RICC problems are characterized by a concentration and/or velocity field that are functions of more than one spatial dimension, and/or reaction kinetics that are anisotropic along the surface.

There are a multitude of factors that influence the multi-dimensionality of the cleaning problem. The shape of the part, the arrangement of a set of parts, and the size of the system container are geometric reasons that make the problem multi-dimensional. Also, if the fluid has to navigate corners and obstructions in the path of flow, the velocity field becomes multi-dimensional, and hence the concentration field. Evolution of gases in the form of bubbles during the reaction step, brings into play interfacial hydrodynamics, which is another contributing factor to the multi-dimensionality of the problem. So is any externally applied force on the fluid, such as that due to pumping and agitation. In regards to reaction kinetics, the reaction rates could vary along the surface due to the factors described in equation (4). This immediately sets up concentration gradients, and destroys any uni-directionality.

Analyzing multi-dimensional cleaning problems is not a simple task. The fundamentals that lead to its scientific description are well established, though considerably mathematical,

and involve solving the mathematical forms for the following laws - *conservation of mass, conservation of momentum, conservation of etchant species, and/or conservation of energy*. Also, these mathematical forms are so complex that it is necessary to use powerful computational techniques such as *the finite element method (FEM)* to obtain solutions [6]. The key features of the analysis of multi-dimensional RICC problems are illustrated below, using a model 2-D problem simulated under isothermal conditions.

6.1 RICC simulation in a 2-D tank

RICC can be done in a variety of systems. Immersion of parts in a tank containing etchants is one of them and will be the focus in this section. Figure 7 shows a schematic sketch of the model problem. The inset shows the direction of view. The fluid is maintained at a constant velocity (U) in the x -direction, on the top side of the domain. This causes the fluid to move in the tank, with the flow being in circular motion. The problem is two

dimensional since the velocity and concentration variables are functions of the x and y directions, but not the z direction. The contaminated part to be cleaned is located between $x = 0.35$ and $x = 0.65$ at the bottom of the tank, and extends along the entire length in the z-direction. The part will be considered to be thin, so that it can be taken to be flush with the bottom of the tank. Note that this need not be the case always, since the simulation can be done with the part located anywhere in the tank and of arbitrary size. The analysis will be carried out for the initial stages of etching, so that a quasi steady state analysis can be used. Therefore, initial conditions are not required. However, boundary conditions still need to be applied. For the velocity it is zero on the left, right and bottom sides, and U on the top side. For the etchant concentration the boundary condition is one of zero flux on all sides, except where the contaminant is present, since the flux here is equal to the rate of reaction.

The first step in tackling this problem is to non-dimensionalize all variables. The velocity, concentration and distance variables have been made dimensionless by scaling with the velocity at the top of the domain (U), the bulk etchant concentration (C_{A1}) and the horizontal container length (L) respectively. The reason that this is done is to reduce the number of independent variables that the problem depends on. By doing this several dimensionless groups are formed and the problem can be studied by varying these, since they are more physically descriptive. The group that arises from the conservation of momentum is the Reynolds number (Re_L based on tank length) and that from the conservation of etchant species is the bulk Peclet number (Pe_B). These are defined here.

$$Re_L = \text{Reynolds number} = \frac{\text{Inertial forces}}{\text{Viscous forces}} = \frac{L U \rho}{\mu} \quad (19)$$

$$Pe_B = \text{Peclet number (bulk)} = \frac{\text{Etchant transport by convection}}{\text{Etchant transport by diffusion}} = \frac{U L}{D_A} \quad (20)$$

A dimensionless group also arises from the boundary condition for the etchant along the contaminant interface, and is called the Damkohler number (Da).

$$Da = \text{Damkohler number} = \frac{\text{Rate of chemical reaction}}{\text{Rate of etchant transfer by diffusion}} = \frac{k_r L}{D_A} \quad (21)$$

After casting the cleaning problem in dimensionless form, the actual simulation was carried out using a finite element computer code. The code was written in FORTRAN and run on a Pentium based PC. The mathematical details of this method are beyond the scope of this paper and can be found in other references [6, 7 and 8]. However, for the purpose of this discussion it is sufficient to note that the computations give values of velocity and concentration at a specified number of points in the problem domain. In this study these variables were computed at 441 points, placed at equal distances in the domain. The results from this simulation are depicted in Figures 8(a) to 8(f).

The base case is simulated with $Re_L = 1.0$, $Pe_B = 100$ and $Da \rightarrow \infty$. Reynolds number being set to one implies that both viscous and inertial forces are present in the fluid, with the former exhibiting greater influence. On the other hand the large value of bulk Peclet number implies that the etchant moves much faster by convection than by molecular diffusion. The Damkohler number being set to infinity signifies that the reaction at the interface is instantaneous, and that mass transport is the limiting factor. Also, this would result in the etchant concentration at the interface to be zero. Figure 8 (a) shows the computed velocity field for this case. Note that the arrows in this figure are proportional to the fluid velocity. The resulting concentration field is depicted in figure 8(b) as a contour plot. Successive lines have concentration differences of 0.05 dimensionless units. For quick reference the legend to the right of the figure shows the actual concentration values of each label. When the lines are close together it implies that the etchant flux is large. At the right end of the contaminant (around $x = 0.6$) the flux is the highest and equal to 8.9 dimensionless flux units. This flux reduces in magnitude as one moves to the left ($x = 0.4$). The average flux along the contaminant interface is found to be 5.8 dimensionless units. Note that for a given system the dimensionless flux can be converted to dimensional etch rates, measured in m/s, by multiplying with $(b M D_A c_A / L \rho_B)$. The message that this simulation puts forth is that in dynamic 2-D cleaning problems the etch rate along the contaminant interface varies and that it is influenced by the flow pattern.

The etchant transport by convection was at least two orders of magnitude larger than that by molecular diffusion, in the base case discussed above ($Pe_B = 100$). When diffusion happens to dominate the mass transport, which is done easily by simulating with $Pe_B = 0$, the results are dramatically different, as shown by the concentration contour plots in figure 8 (c). The characteristic trends of this plot are symmetry about the center, uniform etchant flux above $y = 0.5$, and slightly increased flux around the contaminant edges. For this simulation the average etch rate was computed to be 3.0 dimensionless units, which is approximately half that in the base case. This shows that convective mass transport can enhance the rate of contaminant cleaning.

The previous two simulations stipulated that the reaction was infinitely fast at the contaminant interface ($Da \rightarrow \infty$). This implied that the cleaning was limited by the mass transport of etchant. This need not be the case always since in many real cleaning problems both the reaction rate and mass transport are important. This case is simulated here by setting $Da = 10$, and the resulting contour plot is shown figure 8 (d). The plot indicates that the etchant concentration at the contaminant interface varies between 0.6 and 0.9 dimensionless units, and that concentration gradients are low, even around the edges of the contaminant. Further, the average etch rate is found to be 1.8 dimensionless units, which is roughly one third of that in the base case. This shows that cleaning rates can be considerably affected by the chemistry, since it is the chemistry that is responsible for different rates of reaction, which influences the Damkohler number.

Figure 8 (a) : Velocity field for $Re_L = 1$, $Pe_B = 100$, $Da \rightarrow \infty$
 Length of the largest vector, shown on the top boundary, is of magnitude 1 unit.

Figure 8 (b) : Concentration field for $Re_L = 1$, $Pe_B = 100$, $Da \rightarrow \infty$

Figure 8 (c) : Concentration field for $Re_L = 1$, $Pe_B = 0$, $Da \rightarrow \infty$

Figure 8 (d) : Concentration field for $Re_L = 1$, $Pe_B = 100$, $Da = 10$

Figure 8 (e) : Velocity field for $Re_L = 500$, $Pe_B = 100$, $Da \rightarrow \infty$
 Length of the largest vector, shown on the top boundary, is of magnitude 1 unit.

Figure 8 (f) : Concentration field for $Re_L = 500$, $Pe_B = 100$, $Da \rightarrow \infty$

Finally, the dependence of cleaning on the intensity of fluid flow is simulated by increasing the Reynolds number. Figures 8 (e) and 8 (f) show the velocity field and concentration contours for $Re_L = 500$. Note that the magnitude of velocity at each point in the domain is larger than that in the base case (Figure 8 (a)). Also, the value of etchant fluxes are larger than that in the base case. The computed average etch rate is found to be 8.0 dimensionless units. Therefore, in predicting cleaning rates one has to take into account the strength of the flow field too.

7.0 The next step

Application of the RICC principles presented in this paper would be the next logical step for professionals who process parts and for those who develop new cleaning specifications. The recommended starting point is to actually carry out simple experiments and test the applicability of the 1-D models presented in section 5.0. The experiments can be performed on test pieces in a laboratory setting or in an actual processing unit. The change in thickness as etching progresses can be conveniently measured using a micrometer or a profilometer. An instrument resolution in the micron range should be sufficient, since it is characteristic of most cleaning situations. Examples of these methods can be found in the paper by *Klein and D Stefan*[9], who have studied the etch rates of silicon in HF-HNO₃ systems, and in the paper by *Otsubo et al.*, on the etching of gallium arsenide [10]. If a finer measurement resolution is required optical microscopy or scanning electron microscopy (SEM) can be used, but this would limit the size of test pieces. *Kuiken et al.* [5] and *Alkire et al.* [11] have used this approach in their etching studies. There are still other methods for thickness measurement, such as those based on ellipsometry and interference techniques [12,13]. These methods take advantage of the transparency of surfaces to visible light and/or other electromagnetic radiation.

Suppose one of the 1-D models is applicable in a given cleaning situation, then prediction of etch rates at other process conditions can be done with the help of the mathematical expressions developed in this paper. However, if resources permit, experimental verification should also be performed. As an exercise one can test the validity of 1-D models to the experimental results of *Schwartz and Robbins*, who show that the etching of silicon in acidic solutions is linear with temperature [14]. They also demonstrate that different crystal orientations of the same material exhibit varying etch rates under identical conditions. This work is a practical example that illustrates the complex nature of reaction rate expressions, such as equation (4).

Multi-dimensional problems are an inevitable aspect of cleaning parts on a production scale. Section 6.0 illustrated the role of dimensionless groups in the analysis of 2-D cleaning problems and the use of computational tools. Such simulations have a lot of appeal since process conditions can be changed by varying the dimensionless groups and obtaining cleaning results at the click of a button. Though the initial effort that goes into developing a computational code is considerable, the end result is a tool that can predict cleaning rates

quickly. It may be noted that unsteady state aspects of multi-dimensional problems have not been addressed in this work, since steady state problems were sufficient to illustrate the key aspects. Those interested in time dependent problems should refer to literature for more information [7, 8, 15 and 16].

The spectrum of materials and cleaning chemicals available for RICC are as vast as the field of chemistry and, therefore, readily available etching data is scarce. Much of the data that is available is scattered in a multitude of scientific areas. With careful research and analysis this gap can be bridged. In doing so one should keep in focus the basic principles that govern RICC, especially mass transport, reaction kinetics and the role of fluid dynamics.

8.0 Nomenclature

a,b,p,r,s,	Stoichiometric coefficient of chemical species
c_i	Molar concentration of species i, Kgmol/m^3
c_A	Molar concentration of etchant, Kgmol/m^3
c_{Al}	Bulk concentration of etchant, Kgmol/m^3
k_f	Reaction rate constant, m/s (based on equation (6))
k_m	Convective mass transfer coefficient, m/s
k_{meq}	Effective mass transfer coefficient, m/s (equation (10))
r_B	Reaction rate of contaminant, $\text{Kgmol/m}^2\text{s}$
r_i	Reaction rate of species i, $\text{Kgmol/m}^2\text{s}$
t	Time, s
y_i	Location of contaminant interface at time = t, m
x,y,z	Co-ordinate axes
A	Etchant
B	Contaminant
H	Initial thickness of contaminant, m
L	Characteristic length, m
P	Parent material to be cleaned
R,S	Product materials
U	Velocity scale, taken to be the maximum velocity in the domain, m/s
M_B	Molecular weight of contaminant, Kg/Kgmol
$N_{i,y}$	Molar/mass flux of species i in the y-direction, $\text{Kgmol/m}^2\text{s}$
D_i	Diffusion coefficient of species i in a fluid mixture, m^2/s
D_A	Diffusion coefficient of species A in etchant mixture, m^2/s
$D_{A,\text{eff}}$	Effective diffusion coefficient of etchant species A in the smut layer, m^2/s
L_x	Linear distance along contaminant interface measured from the leading edge, m
J_i	Molecular flux of species i w.r.t. the molar average velocity, $\text{Kgmol/m}^2\text{s}$
Da	Damkohler number, dimensionless
Pe_B	Bulk Peclet number, dimensionless
Re_x, Re_L	Reynolds number, dimensionless
Sh	Sherwood number, dimensionless

Sc	Schmidt number, dimensionless
α_j	Constants in etch rate equations ($j = 1,2,3,4$), m/s
β	Factor used in evaluating the coefficient y , dimensionless
γ	Coefficient appearing in equation (17), dimensionless
μ	Fluid viscosity, N-s/m ²
ρ	Fluid density, Kg/m ³
ρ_B	Mass density of contaminant, Kg/m ³
∇	Gradient vector
Δ	Symbol for the difference between two quantities

9.0 References

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